

Najran

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Early Christianity, Religious Place, Abrahamic, Archaeological Site, Arabia

South Arabia was unified under the kingdom of Ḥimyar around 275 CE, after subjugating the nearby kingdoms of Saba' and Ḥaḍramawt. The king of Ḥimyar Malkīkarib Yuha'min (reigned from about 375 to 400) converted to monotheism around 380. Two religious communities are in South Arabia during the fourth and fifth centuries. A local Jewish community influenced the ruling elites, which adopted a cautious form of monotheism which could be defined as "Jewish sympathizing". In addition to the presence of several Hebrew and Aramaic loanwords in Ḥimyarite inscriptions, two Hebrew inscriptions have been found in South Arabia and a group of epitaphs found outside South Arabia has been attributed to Jewish Ḥimyarite emigrants. The Ḥimyarite kings' choice to adopt a monotheism inspired by Judaism potentially had political implications, distancing Ḥimyar from Christian political entities, such as Rome, Aksum, and the surrounding federations of Arabia. Two centuries after the unification, Christianity spread in South Arabia from Najrān, an oasis located at the intersection of the trade route between South Arabia and North-Western Arabia. While one literary account attributes the spread of Christianity in Najrān to a priest by the name of 'Azqir, active at the time of king Shurih'īl Yakkuf (ca. 468-80), others attributes it to a trader named Ḥannān or Ḥayyān who had converted at Ḥīrah, in modern Iraq. Another literary account attributes the Ḥimyarite's conversion to Christianity to the preachings of the ascetics Paul and John. This hagiography was probably the basis of the narrative by the Yemeni Wahb ibn Munabbih (d. 728/32) reported by the Muslim historians Ibn Ishāq and al-Tabarī. Both authors claim that two Christians, named Faymiyūn and Ṣālih, were sold as enslaved people in Najrān, where people venerate palm trees. When Faymiyūn proved the truthfulness of the Christian God, the oasis converted to Christianity. Around 523, the Jews of Ḥimyar, sponsored by the king, and the rising community of Christians of South Arabia entered into conflict when the Jewish South Arabian king by the name of Joseph killed the Christian population of Najrān. Kāleb, the Christian king of Aksum (located between north Ethiopia and south Eritrea) led an expedition to South Arabia and killed Joseph in 525. Thereafter, a Christian kingdom was established in the region until its fall in 575. Kaleb is regarded as a defender of the Miaphysite faction and a saint for the universal church. The kingdom of South Arabia collapsed in the second half of the sixth century.

Date Range: 500 CE - 575 CE

Region: The site of Najran, South Arabia, including the archaeological site of Hima.

Region tags: Arabian Peninsula

The site of Najran, South Arabia, including the archaeological site of Hima.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Irfan Shahīd, *The Martyrs of Najran: New Documents*. *Subsidia hagiographica*, no. 49 (Société des Bollandistes, Brussels, 1971).
- Source 2: Christian Julien Robin, Ali B. Ibrahim Al-Chabban, and Fāyiz Al-Sa'īd. "Inscriptions antiques de la région de Najrān (Arabie séoudite méridionale): nouveaux jalons pour l'histoire de l'écriture, de la langue et du calendrier arabes." *Comptes rendus des séances de l'Académie des Inscriptions et Belles-Lettres* 158, no. 3 (2014): 1033-1128.
- Source 3: Valentina A. Grasso, *Pre-Islamic Arabia. Societies, Politics, Cults and Identities during Late Antiquity* (Cambridge University Press, 2023).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.google.com/maps/place/Najran+Saudi+Arabia/@17.5416739,41.9508874,7z/data=!4m5!3m4!1s0x15feeb07c88f9155:0xd1a779128894f48>
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.najran.gov.sa/Pages/default.aspx>
- Source 2 Description: official website of the city.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

— Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: Since 2007, a Franco-Saudi Archaeological Mission of Najrān (MAFSN), co-directed by Pr. Sa'īd F. al-Sa'īd and Christian Robin, has been investigating the area. In 2014, the mission has focused on the region of Ḥimā, where several epigraphic evidence have been uncovered.

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Franco-Saudi Archaeological Mission of Najrān (MAFSN)

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

↳ Type of elevation

– Mountain

– Other [specify]: Mountain range about a hundred kilometers north-east of Najrān.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Notes: No modifications of the local environment have been uncovered.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Notes: The site is on the desertic edge of the sedentary regions of South Arabia but saw the birth of an urbanized community in the late antique period.

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: Najran is located at the crossroads of caravan trade routes.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Notes: The oasis was known for the wealth produced by local agricultural activities.

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The site was inhabited by a Christian community.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Najran was on the trade route connecting South Arabia to the Levant and the broader Mediterranean World. The oasis was one of the first hubs of the Arabian camel caravan route that linked the Red Sea to northernmost Syria.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– No

Notes: On-going archaeological projects in the surroundings of the oasis have mostly uncovered rock

graffiti.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: No, but several inscriptions bearing crosses and literary sources such as *Martyrium Sancti Arethae* point to the presence of Christian believers and Christian cults on site.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: The inscriptions bearing crosses and personal names point to mere human tombs.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Notes: On the contrary, it looks like the site became a Christian centre in contrast with the official political entity's will.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Notes: However, it looks like the site was inhabited by a Christian community. Although Miaphysitism was probably the dominant Christian denomination in Najrān, other factions were active in the Arabian oasis. For example, the *Chronicle of Seert* suggests that East Syrian Christianity had spread in Najrān by the reign of the Sasanian Yazdagird II (r. 438–57).

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Notes: An Edessan hagiography (probably the basis of the Arabic narrative by the Yemeni Wahb ibn Munabbih (d. 728/32), available in the works by Ibn Ishāq and al-Ṭabarī), claims that two Christians (Faymiyūn and Šālih) were sold as enslaved people in the oasis of Najrān, where people venerate palm trees as their gods. Faymiyūn demonstrated the truthfulness of the Christian God to the ruler of the oasis, leading to the population's conversion to Christianity. Ibn Ishāq and al-Ṭabarī also report a tradition which claims that the missionary activity of a disciple of Faymiyūn called 'Abd Allāh ibn al-Thāmir was needed to establish Christianity in the region.

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Notes: However, the place became known for the massacre of the Christian population of Najran in 523. The Jewish South Arabian ruler Joseph (also known as Dhū Nuwās and Finhās) killed the Christian population of Najrān after the city endured a siege of six months. The inhabitants of Najrān were eventually tricked by Yūsuf into opening the city gates. The Christian leader al-Ḥārith tried to warn the population of Najrān not to trust the Jewish ruler. The massacre ended when the Christian king of Aksūm (in north Ethiopia and south Eritrea), Kāleb (also known as 'Ellā Asbehā), killed Joseph and established a Christian kingdom in the region in 525.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Notes: According to some literary sources, the Christians of Najran were helped by the Christian ruler of Aksum (Ethiopia and Eritrea). However, we have no proof of external sponsorship of the oasis.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The site was inhabited by a Christian community. No specific motivation leading to the establishment of the place have been found. Its favorable position along trade routes likely played a role.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: No traces of a pre-Islamic Arabic Bible have survived.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– No

Notes: All drawings and inscriptions are carved on rocks.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– No

Notes: Decorating crosses are carved on rocks.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Notes: Animals are carved on rocks.

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

Notes: God is not depicted but he is mentioned. Example: "Thawbān son of marthad / Elijah son of Imru' al-Qays son of / God... / Taym".

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

Notes: There is only one god. There are no lesser divine beings such as angels.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: One of the inscriptions is accompanied by two flute players, a man and a woman identified by personal names.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The animals (e.g. camel) are carved next to the Ancient South Arabian epigraphic evidence.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– No

↳ Floral motifs

– No

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Crosses.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: Although some inscriptions are elevated or bearable visible with certain lights.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

Notes: God is not depicted in the region.

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Several inscriptions only contain personal names, pointing to their identification as epitaphs.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Notes: No mosaics are known from this region.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

Notes: The inscriptions often bear dates, making them useful historical sources.
Example: "Thawbān (son of) mālik In the month of burak of the year 364".

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– Yes

Notes: They mostly appear as epitaphs, bearing the drawing of a cross, personal names and the name of god.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: As an example, one of the inscriptions bearing a cross states "Thawbān (son of) Mālik In the month of burak from the year 364".

↳ Other type of decoration:
– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:
– No
Notes: No, but several epitaphs have been discovered.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:
– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:
– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:
Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.
– No

Are grave goods present:
– No

Are formal burials present:
– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:
– Yes

Notes: God is invoked in inscriptions as "God". For example: "Thawbān son of Marthad, Elijah son of Imru' al-Qays son of Taym, oh God (l:'lh)".

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The god invoked as "The God" appears to be the Christian God. No further details are added.

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The god of the Jewish sympathizers of South Arabia is often invoked as "Lord the Heaven". No such a mention has been found in Najran and surroundings.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

Notes: It is unclear whether the community of Najran was considered to be part of the kingdom of Himyar. They venerated a different god and seem to have been somehow autonomous.

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: This is an assumption on the basis of the Najranites' veneration of the Christian god.

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: No.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: No inscription or literary source mentions direct communication between god and believers.

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Notes: Angels, demons and jinn are not attested in the epigraphic corpus of South Arabia. Monumental polytheistic inscriptions are attested only until the fourth century.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: There are no attestation of pilgrimages to Najran, but the presence of the oasis on a lucrative network of trade routes does not exclude the possibility of Christian traders visiting the oasis and worshipping on site.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: No bishop of Najran is attested before the massacre of the Christian population of the city.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No

Notes: According to literary sources, the leader of Najran was the most prominent religious man of the oasis. He died during the massacre of 523.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Notes: South Arabia's wealth was based on trade in frankincense, perfumes, and spices. Najran played a role in the caravan trade of these goods.

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– No

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Notes: Only a few scattered receipts on palm leaves survive from South Arabia. None of them come from Najran.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: No religious material composed in Najran in this period survives. However, an hymn by the Miaphysite John Psaltes 'Calligraphus' (d. ca. 600), abbot of the monastery of John Bar Aphtonius at Qënneshrë (Syria) was dedicated to the Christian martyrs of Najrān.

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